

ABBREVIATION OF LANGUAGE/LINGUISTICS AND LANGUAGE SKILL TERMINOLOGY FOR THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING (ELT)

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Abstract. *The article is dedicated to the role of thematic categories of linguistics and language skills in the terminological system of ELT. The main focus is on abbreviation as a morphological way of production of new terms. Consequently, the types of abbreviations are presented in the article as terminological units related to terminological fields of language and language skills. Moreover, the terminological field of language /linguistics deals with the units related to the theory of language and is represented by the terminological elements common to language variants as one of the specifications of English language teaching (ELT). In addition, language skills are also depicted as one of the ELT terminological fields, thus having peculiar to ELT abbreviations. To understand the linguistic specifications of language and language skill terminology the abbreviated terms are classified in the article.*

Keywords: *ELT terminology, terminological field, language/ linguistics terms, language skill terms, abbreviation, initialisms, shortening, acronyms.*

Introduction

Being one of the ways of formation of new words, abbreviation as a linguistic phenomenon stimulates the shaping of terms in the English Language Teaching (ELT) area. Abbreviations has become a common part of communication among ELT professionals thus making it frequently used on ELT live webinars and offline discussions. Consequently, the appearance of new concepts has given rise to the increase of new terms in the lexical layers of the terminology for ELT. In most cases these new terms tend to be long and complex to be used in speech. So, the tendency to practice abbreviated ELT vocabulary has marked the requirements of speech economy to create an effective professional communication with least effort, as a model once proposed by George Kingsley Zipf, an American professor of philology at Harvard University, in his book “Human Behavior and the Principle of Least Effort” [12,179] also known as “the law of speech savings” [8,75]. Therefore, due to the significant social changes abbreviations in the ELT terminology are coming into being, thus providing an opportunity for the human to spend less mental and physical efforts in achieving specific goals during communication [11, 281-296]. An Uzbek linguist Z.I. Sanakulov, while writing about abbreviations, justify the idea that abbreviations are the result of the process of globalization influencing the language and presenting new words into the language [12,186]. The use of abbreviations in terminology can determine the level of development of a language and can be a characteristic feature of a national language [6,82], [2,113]. Abbreviations are considered as a compaction of multicomponent word combinations [3,57-82] because of the availability of numerous elements of the word combinations and the existence of three or more words [13].

Although substantial information about abbreviations and their function in the language is presented far less is known about abbreviations in the terminology for ELT, the elements of

combinations that make ELT terms and the way the abbreviations effect the special language development. Based on the background evidence presented, here we show the linguistic features of the terminological area of ELT and the types of abbreviation the terms form in the course of language development. The need for this research is further highlighted by the theory of Russian scientist A.A.Reformatskiy about terminological homonymes in interdisciplinary fields[4, 319-330]. Drawing on the methodolocial assumptions made by Atik Pujiyanti, Senowarsito, Sukma Nur Ardini [1] the article also examines the structure of ELT abbreviations and their types.

Methods

A descriptive qualitative research has been used to identify the types of abbreviations of terms used for ELT and to explain the knowledge gathered about the concepts of these terms under consideration. The article deals with the data related to the scope of thematic categories grouped in such branches, called terminological fields, as linguistics/language, language skills. The data was obtained from the internet blogs and online dictionaries related to ELT. The data was analyzed in the form of written and oral words.

Results

The linguistic analysis of ELT text analysis shows that term system for ELT comprise abbreviation as a word formation means of production of new terms. Borisov suggests that abbreviations are created by individual components of a sound or a graphic sign [5,37]. The number of terms used in language and language skill area of ELT are shortened from multicomponent words so that it be short and exact in their form and meaning [14]. We also followed the ideas of Tatum Derin and others, describing that abbreviation is necessary to increase pronounceability and familiarity of words [13].

The terminology for ELT represents the following multicomponent terms in the field of language /linguistics:

AE/AmE < American (generally US) English

AE/AusE < Australian English

BBC English < English of British Broadcasting Corporation. It is more or less equals RP (Received Pronunciation)

BE/BrE < British English

CA < Cultivated (“posh”) Australian

CanE < Canadian English

EI(A)L < English as an International (Auxiliary) Language

ELF < English as a Lingua Franca (also known as EIAL)

GAE < General American English (also known as AE/AmE)

IE/IrE < Irish English

NZ(E) < New Zealand English

SA(E) < South African English

RP < Received Pronunciation (“posh” British English/the standard form of British English pronunciation, based on educated speech in southern England.

The following list of multicomponent terms belong to language skill terminological field:

BICS < Basic Interpersonal Communication Skills

CALP < Cognitive Academic Language Proficiency (formal content material, academic learning)

CC < Communicative Competence

ELA/ELD < English Language Acquisition/Development

SUP < Separate Underlying Proficiency (being good in the L2 is different from being good in the L1, therefore we can't use the L1 to help people learn the L2)

TEL < Threshold Level English (the level where people start to communicate independently)

Terminological field of language and linguistics are mostly two – componential words, while field of terms including language and linguistics are four- componential terms. Morphologically the terms are abbreviated to achieve pronounceability and familiarity of terms [9,75]. Abbreviated terms represent a terminological unit consisting of individual sound – or graphic form of terminology combination relating to lexical meaning [10,124]. As there is no scientific approach to the classification of methods for the formation of abbreviations, we divide abbreviations for language and language skill into the following types:

Abbreviations comprised of the initial letters of the multi-word units and are pronounced as a word. These are called acronyms. They do not have a full stop (period) [7,78-79].

Abbreviations consisting of the first letters of a group of words, pronounced individually, not as a word are called initialisms.

Abbreviations formed by keeping the first few letters or the first syllable are called shortening. The pronunciation of the shortened form is the same as the original word. Shortened terms of language /linguistic and language skills can be used as words.

The following table describes the types of abbreviations used in the language and language skill terminological field:

Table 1. Abbreviations for Language and Language skills terminological field.

Terminological field	Types of Abbreviations					
	Shortening	Contractions	Acronyms	Initialisms	Clippings	Syllabic Abbreviations
Language /Linguistics	AmE AusE BrE IrE CanE			AE BBC English CA ELF GAE NZ(E) SA(E) RP		
Language Skills			BICS CALP SUP	CC ELA/EL D TEL		

Discussion

The data collected for this research consist of 20 terms related to ELT terminological system. These are terms related to language/ linguistics and language skill terminological fields. The number of initial abbreviations and acronyms investigated is equal to 15 and shortening include 5 terms.

The bar chart presented below (picture 1.) shows the frequency of abbreviations used for the language and language skills terms.

Considering the abbreviations and their type in multi-component terms we can say that most of the terms used for language and language skill terminological fields comprise lexical abbreviations. Initialisms make ninety percent in language terminological field in comparison to language skills initialisms that comprise forty percent of the whole terms. That is twice as less in number as those in language terms. Shortenings prevail mostly in language terms which is forty percent of the whole words while acronyms are the terms related to language skills terms, which is equal in quantity with the terms for language.

As a result, language and language skill abbreviations occurring in the ELT terminology vary not only in their form but also in lexical meaning which is derived from the graphical representation of most of the terms.

Picture 1. Correlation of abbreviations in the language and language skills terminological field

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